

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A DISCHARGE PROTOCOL FOR STAFF NURSES CARING FOR MENTALLY ILL PATIENTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339656>

Abstract

The main aim of the study was to assess the practice of discharge procedure among the staff nurses and to prepare a discharge protocol to improve the nursing practice in psychiatric wards. Guidelines of practice with rationale were given through the protocol which included step wise procedure during the discharge of mentally ill patient. Objectives: To identify the practices followed by the nurses during the discharge procedure of mentally ill patient by an observation check list & to determine the effectiveness of protocol in terms of gain in practice score. Setting: Study has done in Father Muller Medical College Psychiatric ward in India. Method: An evaluatory approach with one group pre-test and posttest design was adopted for the study. The data was collected by administering a structured observation check list by the investigator before and after implementation of protocol. Result: The result of the study showed there is significant difference in the mean pre-test score with mean of (5.2) and post-test (25.5). Conclusion: The result suggested that the protocol was effective in improving the practice of the staff nurses regarding the discharge procedure. Majority of staff nurses were not aware of the proper discharge procedure and the findings of the study support the need for protocols and educational programmes to improve the practice in staff nurses. Educating the staff nurses with new information can help them to educate the patient and the relatives to prevent complications and readmissions.

Keywords: Discharge; Protocol; effectiveness; implementation; staff nurse.

I. Introduction

Providing quality health care services is a major concern of health care professionals. A review of anxiety disorder surveys in different countries found average lifetime prevalence estimates of 16.6%, with women having higher rates on average. A review of mood disorder surveys in different countries found lifetime rates of 6.7% for major depressive disorder (higher in some studies, and in women) and 0.8% for Bipolar I disorder (WHO). Average prevalence of severe mental disorders is at least 1.8-2/1000 population; about 3-5 times of this number suffers from other forms of distressing and socio economically incapacitating emotional disorders. Incidence of new cases with serious mental disorders is about 35 per lack population. The probability of readmission within 2 years period after discharge from the first hospitalization is about 40-60%. A proper discharge procedure can only become reality, when, psychiatric team keep themselves with latest management protocols.

II. Materials & Method

This study was conducted in Father Muller Medical College Psychiatric ward in Mangalore, India. Pre experimental, one group pre-test post-test design. Thirty staff nurses having minimum two months of experience in the psychiatric ward were selected with their consent. A pre-test with the observational

checklist was done to a total of 30 subjects following which a copy of the protocol was given to each respondent and the post-test was done with the same observational check list after seventh day. The six areas of observation i.e., drugs, (12 items, 30%), warning signs of relapse (10 items, 25%), psycho education (8 items, 20%), follow up (5 items, 12.5%), home care (3 items, 7.5%) and suicide (2 items, 5%). Each item was rated „Yes“ rating as 1 and „No“ as 0 scores. Maximum available score is 40 and least is 0. Whereas poor practice scored <20, average practice scored 21-26, good practice scored 27-33 and very good practice score 34-40. Thirty discharge procedures were observed by the researcher himself. It took 52 days to complete the study and researcher was not concealed and also not participated in the discharge procedure. The researcher observed the discharge procedure while sitting in the nurse’s station. The nurse and the researcher’s distance were two feet, so that the researcher can hear the nurses’ conversation with the patient and the relatives. Researcher was visible by the nurse and the nurse had the idea that the researcher is observing the procedure. Post-test was administered on the seventh day by using the same observation checklist.

III. Results

Data analysis done by Comparison of pre and post test scores. Results in terms of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Data analysed for statistical significance using paired “t” test and hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. Most of the staff nurses (97%) were between 21 -25 years and also most of them (83%) went through the General Nursing and Midwifery course and the rest of them (17%) completed the B.Sc nursing degree. They (83%) had clinical experience for 1 to 5 years and 14% with 0 to 1 years of experience and only 3% were with more than 10 years of clinical experience. The information on discharge procedure was not received by the staff nurses, after completion of their course. All the staff nurses 100% had not received any additional information on discharge procedure after the completion of their course. Majority of the staff nurses (97%) had undergone formal training about discharge procedure during nursing course with an exception of (3%) one, who never got any formal training about discharge procedure.

Table 1 shows the Frequency, percentage and cumulative frequency distribution of pre-test and post test practice scores

Practice score	Pre test			Post test		
	f	%	cf	f	%	cf
0-5	21	70	21			
6-10	8	27	29			
11-15	1	3	30	4	13	4
16-20				-	-	4
21-25				10	33	14
26-30				9	30	23
31-35				7	27	30
36-40						

Fig 1: shows the distribution of sample according to the grade.

Table 2 shows: Range, Mean, Median and Standard deviation of pre and post test practice score of discharge procedure. This recognizes higher practice scores, range (12-34), mean (25.5), median (26) and standard deviation (6.123) in post-test when compared to their pre-test scores, range (2-11) mean (5.2), median (4.5) and standard deviation (2.074).

Practice Area	Range	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Pre test	2-11	5.2	4.5	2.074
Post test	12-34	25.5	26	6.123

Fig 2 shows area wise distribution of Mean percentage pre and post test practice scores

Table 3 shows : the Mean, Mean difference, Standard deviation, and „t“ value of pre and post test practice scores of the staff nurses. This shows that mean post-test practice score (25.5) was higher than the mean pre-test practice score (5.2). the computed „t“ value („t“(29)=2.01) is higher than the tabled value („t“(58)=2.000, P<0.05) hence the null hypothesis is rejected and research hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance, that is the mean difference between pre and post test practice score was a true difference and not a chance difference. This indicates the significant effectiveness of the discharge protocol in increasing the practice of staff nurses.

Mean practice score

Mean

Group	Pre-test	Post-test	difference	SD	‘t’ value
Staff nurses	5.2	25.5	20.3	6.123	2.01*

„t“(29)= 2.000 ; (P<0.05)

* significant

Table 4 shows: Area wise pre and post test practice scores of staff nurses on discharge procedure and signifies the highest improvement of practice regarding drugs and warnings signs of relapse and the least practice improvement required regarding the explanation of suicide and its management.

Sl. No.	Area	Total	Pre-test	Posttest	Pre-test	Posttest	Actual gain (A)	Possible gain (B)	Mean Modified score (B-A)
1	Drugs	12	3.96	7.63	33	64	31	67	36
2	Warning signs of relapse	10	0.03	7.23	3	72.3	69.3	97	27.7
3	Psycho education	8	0.26	4.7	3.3	59	55.7	96.7	41
4	Follow up	5	0.93	2.86	18.6	57.2	38.6	81.4	42.8
5	Home care	3	0	2.2	0	73.3	73.3	100	26.7
6	Suicide	2	0	0.86	0	43	43	100	57

Table 5 : Area wise Mean practice score, Mean difference standard deviation and „t“ value of pre and post test practice scores

Area	Mean		difference	SD	‘t’ value
	Pre test	Post test			
Drugs	3.96	7.63	3.6	1.79	11.88*
Warning signs of relapse	0.03	7.23	7.2	1.88	21.17*
Psycho education	0.26	4.7	4.43	1.36	21.43*
Follow up	0.93	2.86	1.93	0.77	13.48*
Home care	0	2.2	2.2	0.80	14.96*
Suicide	0	0.86	0.86	0.62	7.54*

(„t“₍₂₉₎ =2.000, p<0.05)

* significant

IV. Discussion

The study intends to compare and evaluate the Effectiveness of the protocol for the staff nurses on the discharge program of mentally ill patients. The present study showed the protocol is effective, i.e., (t=2.01). Nurses those who are using this protocol should know the basic procedures of psychiatric nursing i.e. the techniques of communication, inter personal relationship, and how to give the respect of culture, custom,

value, belief and understand the needs of the consumer. To do a proper practice along with the skill there is a need to develop nurses' attitude.

The study reflected that during preparation of a type of practice, some of the characteristics of the personals are important and which has correlation with the outcome of the services.³ Present study result also may be affected by the characteristics of the staff nurses. Posttest mean score is 25.5(63%) where maximum score is 40 (100%). That shows there is certain motivational factors which is influencing the outcome of the practice.

The findings of the study showed that Mean post-test practice score (25.5) was higher than the Mean Pre-test practice score (5.2). The computed „t“ value („t“₍₂₉₎ =20.01) is higher than the tabled value („t“₍₂₉₎ =2.000, P<0.05). The mean difference between pre and posttest practice score was a true difference and not a chance difference. This indicates the significant effectiveness of the discharge protocol in increasing the practice of staff nurses. These findings were consistent with the findings of other research studies in which they found that post test scores were high after the implementation of the protocol.

The findings of the present study were analyzed and discussed with the findings of other study similar studies. This helped the investigator to prove that the findings are true and the protocol was effective in improving knowledge.

V. Conclusion

The main aim of the study was to assess the practice of discharge procedure among the staff nurses and to inform them about it. Psychiatric nurses face a lot of difficulties in the area of patient care, because most of the hospital lacking standardized practice guidelines or tests. The scientific and evidence-based knowledge and a problem based practice and communication techniques will help to improve the discharge procedure which is important to prevent complication during home care. The staff nurses need to be updated with knowledge and competence which is a combination of attitude and skill. Staff development programmes through continuous education and training, teaching and learning materials like protocol are major factors in shaping the future of the profession of psychiatric nursing services. The findings of the study have several implications for nursing service, education, administration and research.

Acknowledgement

I would like to acknowledge Mr. Suresh Kumar, statistician for his expert guidance and support, in statistical analysis.

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